

Interview with Japanese Singer and Model Nana Kitade at FicZone 2023

Andrés Domenech Alcaide

CoolJapan.es

About Nana Kitade

Nana Kitade is a Japanese artist whose career has focused on music and modelling. She is originally from Sapporo, in Hokkaidō, in northern Japan, and from a very early age—at just three years old—she already showed artistic talent, being able to play the piano. Formal studies did not particularly appeal to her from a young age, and she always felt that her path lay in learning about the arts—although she did not abandon her education and eventually graduated from the Hokkaidō University of Education. She learned to play the guitar during secondary school and frequently travelled to Tokyo to study singing.

In 2002, she was selected from nearly 40,000 participants to represent the Sapporo area in an audition held by Sony Music, marking the beginning of her career as a singer. She spent some time writing lyrics before choosing as her debut single the song *Kesenai Tsumi* (“*Indelible Sin*”), released in 2003 and widely known as the first ending theme of the anime *Fullmetal Alchemist*.

Kitade began her career with a pop rock style but gradually shifted towards pop punk and the Gothic Lolita aesthetic, which had developed in Japan through artists such as Mana —Satō Manabu— of the band Malice Mizer. She stood out within this aesthetic thanks to her personal approach and is now considered one of its leading figures in Japan.

She has been part of several bands, such as Loveless (2009–2012) and The Teenage Kissers (2012–2016). Since 2016, she has been in a new solo phase, releasing her first album of this period, Violet Blaze, in 2017. Her music has featured in opening and ending themes for various series, films, and television programmes, and she has also appeared as a model on covers of magazines such as Gothic & Lolita Bible, Neo, and Kera.

Kitade celebrated her 20th anniversary as a professional singer in 2023, and her international tour included stops in Canada, Hungary, France, the United Kingdom, and Spain (Granada).

From both a professional and personal perspective, having met her in person, we can only speak highly of her. When she met with us, she was in the middle of her tour, and as her appearance had been announced unexpectedly, we had very little time to request an interview with her at FicZone. Both she and her manager were open to it, despite the fact that she had just arrived from a flight, had barely had time to eat, and had performed her concert only minutes before speaking with us. Always smiling and kind, with seemingly boundless energy and curiosity, Nana Kitade is exactly as you see her on stage: fully devoted to her art, with a genuine passion and gratitude towards her fans.

Interview with Nana Kitade

Cool Japan: First of all, we would like to say that we met you in Alicante a few years ago. We would like to congratulate you—on behalf of myself and the entire CoolJapan.es team—on your 20 years as a professional singer, and thank you for taking the time to speak with us, especially as you have just finished a concert—which we attended, in fact.

Nana Kitade: Wow! Thank you very much!

CJ: We know that you were able to play the piano from a very young age, but at that time... was music just a hobby, or were you already thinking about pursuing a career in music? Did you consider doing something else when you grew up?

NK: Not the piano itself, but I've loved music since I was little. Singing and composing as well. There was something else I always wanted to be: a fashion designer.

CJ: You made your debut as a singer after passing an audition for Sony Music. What was the first thing you wanted to do at that moment?

NK: The first thing I thought was that I wanted to make my own album. I had always written my own lyrics, since I was young, but not the music. I usually work with people who compose original music for my lyrics. I thought I could write both the music and the lyrics myself.

CJ: Speaking of that audition, which had nearly 40,000 participants... what was that experience like? You have even worked with Susumu Nishikawa, a musician who has also collaborated with your favourite singer, Ringo Sheena.

NK: I was only 16 at the time when I started... I had no idea how everything worked! I didn't know any of these people... it was actually the other way around... they already knew me! It was very surprising.

Nana Kitade during her concert in Granada

CJ: Speaking of the fashion world, in which you are also involved, are you aware that you have been a guiding light for many enthusiasts of the “Gothic Lolita” style, and, more generally, for your personal aesthetic? You have even worked as a designer. How did you reach this point, and how does it make you feel? Even people close to me, and I myself, were aware of your particular use of this aesthetic.

NK: I am just another fan of the Gothic Lolita style. I don't consider myself a top figure in this fashion world... What happens is that, having appeared in so many magazines [Kitade briefly glances at her outfit, the one you can see in the photographs accompanying this interview]... over time I have received many messages from fans and emails from

people who entered this world looking up to me... taking me as a model, and... [Smiles] that makes me very proud!

I love it! Thank you very much. I was told this doesn't happen only in Japan, but worldwide. Actually, I am like this naturally: I have many different styles, and Gothic Lolita is one of them, which I really like.

CJ: Normally, in anime series, theme songs are selected to accompany the series. But has it ever happened that you composed a song specifically with a series or character in mind, hoping that it would become part of a production or associate with a character or story in your mind?

NK: Yes, I have been commissioned to create songs for a series, and inspiration for the song has come from reading the original work [referring to *Fullmetal Alchemist* and her song *Kesenai Tsumi*, used as the series' ending theme].

Mostly, in my free time, I watch films, read comics, and write lyrics, but the ideas for my song lyrics usually come to me beforehand, though I also write lyrics while reading these things.

Sometimes, the lyrics I have already released are so well received that the producer chooses a song because they already know it and love it. I experienced this, for instance, with a song I created called *Tsukihana* [“*Moon Flower*” in English], for the anime *Hell Girl*.

I had already composed the song without knowing anything about that work... and it practically remained unchanged for its use in the anime.

CJ: Of all the musical genres you have worked in, which do you enjoy the most? Or which would you like to work with in the future?

NK: I am someone who works with many different musical genres... I grew up listening to jazz, rock, and other Western music genres, and I am also familiar with J-Pop, having worked in a variety of styles... [While speaking, she laughs and exchanges a playful comment with Michie Yamaya, our interpreter for this interview.] And now I know flamenco!

I have never worked with flamenco before, so I wonder... what will happen? [Kitade looks thoughtful and amused. After a brief pause, Michie claps a flamenco rhythm, and Kitade starts following the beat, enjoying herself, laughing, and looking at her and then at our colleague.]

It's very difficult! I don't think I can do it!

CJ: Can you tell us if you have any projects in mind for the future related to Europe?

NK: Well, I would love to. I am always writing songs and don't currently have a project like that in the works. I really like Europe, and I would love to go back there. I am particularly fond of European castles such as Neuschwanstein [Germany]. So I knew about it... I have always wanted to work on a project in a European castle, and... I want a European castle... Anyone? [Laughs]

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Nana Kitade for her time and her great attitude, as she had just arrived from a flight, performed a concert minutes before attending us, and endured intense heat for the time of the event, yet treated us with remarkable charm and cordiality. We also thank our interpreter, Michie Yamaya, whose trust with the interviewee greatly facilitated our work.

Additionally, we thank the CrossOver press team and the FicZone management, especially Raúl and Eladia, who made it possible for this interview—which we barely had time to request—to fit into Nana Kitade's tight schedule.

Nana Kitade poses with our colleague Andrés, moments after the interview.

Sources

- **Interview conducted by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es] |
Interview interpreted by: Michie Yamaya
- **Images by:** CrossOver press team

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